

fliF.4

fliF.5

fliF.6

fliF_622.0

fliG.0

fliG.1

fliG.2

fliG.3

fliG_623.0

fliH.0

fliH.1

fliI_0

fliI.0

fliI.1

ppsC.3

wapA

ysoA

leuD

leuC

leuB

1952_mdh.f

phoR

phoP

mdh

icd

